

How much are too many scientific papers? A detailed investigation of hyperprolific authors in the top 2% scientists of the world

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Abstract

Scientific publication metrics provide a way to measure the impact and influence of a publication. These metrics can be used to evaluate the quality and importance of a scientific publication, as well as the research productivity and success of a scientist. While citation is key, citation metrics are closely linked to number of papers. There is anecdotal evidence that some hyperprolific authors can publish a paper within 5 days. This paper examines these authors in detail using the latest top 2% scientists database. The study reveals that some authors can publish, on average, 100-200 papers per year, including single-authored papers. A closer look reveals the flaw of the database and that these authors from medical science are journalists. Some of these journalists were even ranked higher than Nobel laureates. Further investigation exposes some close-connected scientists who publish more than 100 papers per year in environmental sciences and gain incredible number of highly cited paper records. It is concluded that the scientific community has the need to establish ethical guidelines and practices on number of publications to ensure that publishing a paper is conducted with integrity and that the pursuit of knowledge is not compromised by personal interests.

Keywords: citation, highly cited researchers, impact factor.

1. Introduction

Publishing scientific research papers is an important part of a researcher's career, as it allows them to share their findings and ideas with others in their field and to contribute to the body of knowledge in their area of expertise. Publishing papers can also help researchers to establish their reputation and expertise within their field, and can be important for career advancement and professional recognition [1,2].

In many academic and research settings, publishing papers is considered a key indicator of a researcher's productivity and impact. Researchers who have published a high number of papers, or who have published papers in high impact journals, is often seen as more qualified and competitive for research funding, teaching positions, and other opportunities [3].

However, it is important to note that publishing papers is not the only measure of a researcher's contributions or success. Other factors, such as the quality and impact of the research can also be important in evaluating a researcher's career.

Citation metrics are used to measure the impact and influence of a particular publication, scholar, or research group. They are often used in academic contexts to evaluate the quality and significance of research, to compare the relative importance of different publications or researchers, and to identify trends and patterns in research.

Citation metrics are often used in conjunction with other measures of research quality, such as peer review, to evaluate the importance and impact of research. However, they are not perfect and can be subject to manipulation and bias. As such, they should be used cautiously and in conjunction with other indicators of research quality.

Citation metrics are closely linked to number of papers. Research by Larivière and Costas [2] using a large database found that, the higher the number of papers a researcher publishes, the higher the number of highly cited papers. For established researcher, there is an incentive of publishing as many papers as possible. The higher the number of papers a researcher can publish, the more he/she gets known and in turn receive many citations.

However increasing the size of publication, for example, collaborating with a network of researchers, one can publish two or three papers per week. This strategy can boost one's citation as a result of the publishing network coauthors. There is a huge incentive on having a high citation, including the prestigious Highly Cited Researcher by Clarivate and Stanford University's Top 2% Scientists [3,4].

This raises the question how much is too much. Hyperprolific authors are scientists who produce a very large volume of work in a relatively short period of time. These authors may write 2 or 3 or 4 papers per week. Some hyperprolific authors are able to produce so much work that they are considered to be among the most productive writers in history. But is it possible?

Recently, a new ranking from Stanford University features the world's top 2% most influential scientists [3,4]. This list, led by Professor John PA Ioannidis, is compiled using Scopus citation information. This list also offers an analysis of possible hyperprolific authors and their contribution.

Ioannidis et al. [1] wrote "Authorship is the coin of scholarship — and some researchers are minting a lot." A research in biomedical journals reveals a nepotistic behaviour, papers by the most prolific authors were more likely to be accepted for publication within 3 weeks of their submission [5]. Few authors, often members of the editorial board, were responsible for a disproportionate number of publications. Prof Ioannidis further mentioned hyperprolific authors publish a paper every five days. This study aims to discover hyperprolific authors in the top 2% list.

Methods

This paper uses the database "Updated science-wide author databases of standardized citation indicators" by Ioannidis [6] available at <https://elsevier.digitalcommonsdata.com/datasets/btchxktzyw> [4, 6].

The database of top-cited scientists contains standardized information on citations along with career-long and, recent year impact for 22 scientific fields. The selection is based on the top 100,000 scientists by c-score or a percentile rank of 2% or above in the sub-field. The version of this database is based on the Sept 1, 2022 snapshot from Scopus [6].

Results and Discussion

Most productive researchers

The database contains 195,605 authors from 1834 until 2022. This study only focuses on authors who are productive and thus only select authors whose first publication was post 1990. The number of papers published per year was calculated for each author: $np/[2022 - \text{first year publication}]$. The distribution is heavily skewed ranging from 0.01 to 220. According to [1], authors who had published more than 72 papers per year is considered implausibly prolific. Because the total number of papers per year is averaged over a long period, this study considers an average 30 papers per year as implausibly prolific. There are only 894 authors (or 0.46% of the database) that exceed publishing an average 30 papers per year,

Table 1 produces top 20 most productive authors. It is impressive to note that some authors who wrote 70-220 papers over the length of their careers. A deeper analysis reveals that some of the authors (Table 1) are editors from journals. The most prolific author is Elisabeth Mahase, a news reporter at The BMJ, and Scopus considers the news article as "peer review" articles and she has topped most authors in scientific output. Other authors from BMJ include Gareth Iacobucci from BMJ, Abi Rimmer, etc. Most productive non journalist author is Viroj Wiwanitkit who managed to pump out, on average, 146 papers per year. Two prolific authors who have a high c rank are from Aalborg university, Gregory Lip with 116 papers per year and Frede Blaabjerg at 89 papers per year. Other prolific authors came from various countries, including USA, Saudi Arabia, and India.

While not in the top 20, Table 1 includes John P.A. Ioannidis, who has critically published about hyperprolific authors. Ioannidis himself, on average since 1994, publishes 45 papers per year. According to Scopus, in 2016-2021, Ioannidis published 52-80 papers per year, or on average 1 paper over 5 days, "a figure that many would consider implausibly prolific" [1, 7].

Table 1. Most productive researchers according to the Stanford database.

authfull	inst_name	np6021	firstyr	rank (ns)	h21 (ns)	np/years	sm-field
Mahase, Elisabeth	BMJ Dr. D. Y. Patil	661	2019	33363	24	220.3	Clinical Medicine
Wiwanitkit, Viroj	Vidyapeeth, Pune	3366	1999	30078	25	146.3	Clinical Medicine
Iacobucci, Gareth	BMJ	1364	2012	95467	15	136.4	Clinical Medicine
McCarthy, Michael	Seattle	790	2012	142232	13	131.7	Clinical Medicine
Rimmer, Abi	BMJ	864	2014	236367	11	123.4	Clinical Medicine
Lip, Gregory Y.H.	Aalborg University Northwestern Polytechnical University	3484	1992	208	146	116.1	Clinical Medicine
Huang, Wei	Mashhad University of Medical Sciences	2676	1996	12966	127	102.9	Enabling & Strategic Technologies
Sahebkar, Amirhossein	Quaid-i-Azam University	1369	2008	7099	71	97.8	Clinical Medicine
Hayat, T.	Beijing Forestry University	2583	1995	4545	89	95.7	Engineering Enabling & Strategic Technologies
Li, Qiang	University	1100	2010	40004	52	91.7	Technologies
Blaabjerg, Frede	Aalborg University	2750	1991	639	131	88.7	Engineering
Wise, Jacqui	Kent King Abdulaziz University	1231	2007	80007	16	82.1	Clinical Medicine
Alsaedi, Ahmed	King Abdulaziz University	1393	2005	41277	73	81.9	Physics & Astronomy
Asiri, Abdullah M.	University	2034	1997	10200	106	81.4	Chemistry Information & Comm.Technologies
Chen, Jie	Shanghai University European Organization for Nuclear Research	878	2002	84289	39	79.8	Physics & Astronomy
Hoecker, A.	Aix Marseille University	2127	1994	123556	111	76.0	Physics & Astronomy
Aad, G.	Université	1054	2008	26672	84	75.3	Physics & Astronomy
Sayyed, M. I.	Isra University	428	2016	103163	30	71.3	Physics & Astronomy Information & Comm.
Chen, Ming	Yangzhou University	1693	1998	25524	56	70.5	Technologies
Lange, D.	Princeton University	1812	1996	33999	100	69.7	Physics & Astronomy
Ioannidis, John P.A.	Stanford University School of Medicine	1264	1994	32	157	45.1	Clinical Medicine

authfull : author name; inst_name: institution name; firstyr: year of first publication; np6021: # papers 1960-2021; rank (ns): rank based on composite score c, self-citations excluded; h21 (ns) h-index as of end-2021; np/years: # papers per year; sm-field: scientific field.

The number of research papers that a scientist can write in a year depends on many factors, including their research focus, the amount of time they have available to devote to writing, and the complexity of the research being conducted. Some scientists may write several papers in a year, while others may write only one or two. In general, scientists who are actively conducting research and publishing their findings can be expected to write several papers per year, not a paper every week. In addition, scientists who are also teaching or working on administrative tasks may have less time available for writing papers.

It is also important to note that the quality of research papers is more important than the quantity. A scientist who produces a few well-written, high-impact papers may have a greater impact on their field than a scientist who produces a larger number of papers of lower quality.

This study further investigates most prolific authors who have written a paper solely him/herself. Table 2 presents the results. What is more amazing that these authors are all from Clinical Medicine and can single-handedly write over 72 papers per year. But most of these authors are journalists from BMJ and other news outlets. The exception is Viroj Wiwanitkit from Dr. D. Y. Patil Vidyapeeth, a University in Pune who published, on average, 74 papers per year, and Romina Brignardello-Petersen from McMaster University, Canada who published 53 papers per year.

This result highlights the deeply fundamental flaw of the so-called “databases of standardized citation indicators” which do not recognize if an author is a journalist and the articles are news articles [3]. This standardized indicator place value on single-authored and first-author papers made a journalist Elisabeth Mahase who can write a one-page news article every two days has a c rank of #33363, much higher than scientists from MIT, Stanford or any scientist that had to do hard work in experimental research. Journalist Bridget M. Kuehn, according to the Stanford list, is ranked #17026, much higher than 2021 Nobel laureate in Medicine Ardem Patapoutian who has a c rank #28519, and 2022 Nobel Prize winner in physics Alain Aspect, who is ranked #20486. This c rank can be easily misused.

Table 2. Most productive authors with single-authored papers.

authfull	inst_name	nps	rank (ns)	h21 (ns)	nps/years	sm-field
Mahase, Elisabeth	BMJ	653.0	33363	24	217.7	Clinical Medicine
Iacobucci, Gareth	BMJ	1344.0	95467	15	134.4	Clinical Medicine
McCarthy, Michael	Seattle	790.0	142232	13	131.7	Clinical Medicine
Rimmer, Abi	BMJ	848.0	236367	11	121.1	Clinical Medicine
Wise, Jacqui	Kent	1228.0	80007	16	81.9	Clinical Medicine
Wiwanitkit, Viroj	Dr. D. Y. Patil Vidyapeeth, Pune	1714.0	30078	25	74.5	Clinical Medicine
Brignardello-Petersen, Romina	McMaster University	580.0	198767	32	52.7	Clinical Medicine
Hawkes, Nigel	London	861.0	184183	11	50.6	Clinical Medicine
Kuehn, Bridget M.		985.0	17026	28	49.3	Clinical Medicine
Burki, Talha Khan		685.0	61453	19	48.9	Clinical Medicine
Kmietowicz, Zosia	BMJ	1269.0	102462	15	48.8	Clinical Medicine
Torjesen, Ingrid	BMJ	777.0	169388	12	48.6	Clinical Medicine
Abbasi, Jennifer	Univ California, San Francisco	287.0	192207	13	47.8	Clinical Medicine
Mayor, Susan	London	1210.0	101026	14	46.5	Clinical Medicine
O'Dowd, Adrian	BMJ	757.0	309276	9	44.5	Clinical Medicine
Bateman, Chris	BMJ	723.0	332782	8	40.2	Clinical Medicine
Dyer, Owen	BMJ	600.0	150574	14	40.0	Clinical Medicine
Collier, Roger	CMAJ American Medical Association	429.0	147600	14	39.0	Clinical Medicine
Randall, T.	Bay Medical Center,	112.0	236744	13	37.3	Clinical Medicine
Traynor, Kate	Panama City	814.0	225003	11	37.0	Clinical Medicine

authfull : author name; inst_name: institution name; nps: number of single authored papers; rank (ns): rank based on composite score c; h21 (ns) h-index as of end-2021; nps/years: # single authored papers per year.

Science journalists play an important role in communicating scientific ideas, discoveries, and research to the general public. They report on the latest developments in science and technology, explaining complex scientific

concepts in a way that is easy to understand for a non-expert audience. In addition to reporting on scientific topics, science journalists may also write feature articles, conduct interviews with scientists, and produce multimedia content such as videos and podcasts. However they should not be considered as top 2% scientists of the world as widely promoted. In this case of standardized database, Ioannidis [6] wrote “Citation metrics are widely used and misused”, this is such a misuse.

Most productive field of science

It is generally difficult to determine which field of science is the most productive, as different fields have made significant contributions to our understanding of the world and have had a significant impact on society. Some fields, such as physics and chemistry, have a long history and have played a crucial role in the development of modern technology and medicine. Other fields, such as computer science and biotechnology, have emerged more recently and have had a significant impact on the way we live and work.

However, based on number of research papers published, Table 3 identifies the relative productivity of the field of science based on the median and maximum number of papers per year. Clinical medicine is the most productive with a record maximum of 220 papers per year. As discussed above, this is related to news article, a flaw in the database. This is followed by technologies, engineering, physics, chemistry, mathematics, biology and environmental sciences. The least productive authors are in Historical Studies, Philosophy & Theology, and Visual & Performing Arts.

This result is different from previous research who found that the vast majority of hyperprolific authors are in physics [1]. But it is important to note that the contributions of different fields are interconnected and often build upon one another. The Covid-19 pandemic indeed has boosted the number of hyperprolific authors in medicine [7,8,9].

Table 3. Most productive field of science, number of papers per year.

Field	Median np/year	Maximum np/year
Clinical Medicine	6.9	220.3
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	7.1	102.9
Engineering	6.2	95.7
Physics & Astronomy	6.5	81.9
Chemistry	6.6	81.4
Information & Communication Technologies	5.9	79.8
Mathematics & Statistics	4.8	61.6
Biology	4.4	50.5
Earth & Environmental Sciences	5.5	49.8
Economics & Business	3.0	41.6
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	4.8	39.1
Biomedical Research	5.0	38.1
Public Health & Health Services	4.8	34.1
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	4.5	28.3
Social Sciences	2.7	26.6
Built Environment & Design	4.8	23.8
Communication & Textual Studies	2.0	12.7
Historical Studies	1.9	11.1
Philosophy & Theology	2.2	8.2
Visual & Performing Arts	1.5	5.6

Case Study: Most productive authors in Earth & Environmental Sciences

As the analysis presented in the previous sections reflect average number of papers, it is essential to dig deep the analysis of number of papers published in particular years. We take the case study in Earth & Environmental Sciences, where the top most prolific authors are listed in Table 4. It is important to note, out of these authors, only 4 were awarded highly cited researcher by Clarivate in 2022: Yong Sik Ok, Cao Jun Ji, and Hafiz M.N. Iqbal.

Table 4. Most productive authors in Earth & Environmental Sciences

authfull	inst_name	np6021	rank (ns)	h21 (ns)	np/years
Peng, Yongzheng	Beijing University of Technology	996	86590	62	49.8
Huang, Gordon	University of Regina	1396	17927	59	46.5
Ok, Yong Sik	Korea University	714	65797	82	39.7
Cao, Jun Ji	Chinese Academy of Sciences	747	34711	76	35.6
Iqbal, Hafiz M.N.	Tecnologico de Monterrey	422	203470	45	35.2
Sillanpää, Mika	University of Johannesburg	929	8002	82	34.4
Chen, Yangkang	Bureau of Economic Geology	305	42533	40	33.9
Gao, Baoyu	Shandong University	737	89670	70	33.5
Mahvi, Amir Hossein	Tehran University of Medical Sciences	592	40372	48	32.9
Rizwan, Muhammad	Government College University Faisalabad	327	181217	48	32.7
Tsang, Daniel C.W.	Hong Kong Polytechnic University	516	133686	61	32.3

Table 5. Number of papers published by most prolific authors in Earth and Environmental Sciences from 2015-2022 (data from Scopus, November 2022).

Year	Ok	Tsang	Peng	Huang	Iqbal
2015	30	8	66	75	5
2016	63	12	81	85	15
2017	107	49	60	82	42
2018	97	97	46	81	52
2019	116	102	82	70	63
2020	103	135	103	65	89
2021	75	77	79	96	127
2022	86	54	90	82	177

Table 5 displays further information on 4 prolific authors: Yong Sik Ok from Korea University, Daniel Tsang from Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Yongzheng Peng from Beijing University of Technology, Gordon Huang from University of Regina, and M.H.N. Iqbal from Tecnologico de Monterrey. These authors, in general publish more than 72 papers per year (the definition of hyperprolific author). In particular Ok, Tsang, Iqbal and Huang have published more than 100 papers per year.

It is argued that “productivity does not equal usefulness” [10] however some strategies can make it work. There are several strategies that scientists can use to be more productive in their research, and the most important one is collaborating with other scientists can help to expand your knowledge and expertise, and can also help to speed up the research process. In addition, one can use technology effectively: There are many tools and resources available that can help scientists to be more productive, such as software for data analysis and project management.

A curious case is Yong Sik Ok from Korea University and his close collaborator Daniel CW Tsang from Hong Kong Polytechnic University, both have published more than 100 papers a year in 2019 and 2020. Together they have co-authored more than 180 papers. Both of them received boosted citations. According to Web of Science, currently (in November 2022) Yong Sik Ok has 91 highly cited papers and Daniel Tsang has 87 highly cited papers (h-index). Among those, Ok has 28 h-index published in 2019 and 21 h-index for papers in 2020. This means that in 2018 and 2019, Ok published 2 papers every week (fully peer-reviewed and published). And incredibly, every 2 weeks, those papers got highly cited. This assumes working at 365 days a year. An impressive but implausible achievement. Ok and Tsang continuously publish 90 to 120 papers per year, and Clarivate has awarded Ok and Tsang have been rewarded Highly Cited Researcher in multiple fields. Another interesting fact, according to public data at Publons, Daniel Tsang reviews 20–30 papers per month in 2020-2021. Thus he writes a paper every 2 days, and still has time to review 1 paper everyday, including weekends and holidays.

This begs the question, can one write a paper in 2–3 days and get highly cited within 2 weeks? Ioannidis et al. (2018) further wrote that the reasons are: “hard work; love of research; mentorship of very many young researchers; leadership of a research team, or even of many teams; extensive collaboration; working on multiple research areas or in core services; availability of suitable extensive resources and data; culmination of a large project; personal values such as generosity and sharing; experiences growing up; and sleeping only a few hours per day.”

Conclusions

The number of research papers that a scientist can write in a year depends on several factors, including the scientist's research productivity, time commitments, and the availability of funding and resources. Some scientists may be able to write several papers in a year, while others could write more than 100 papers per year. The number of papers that a scientist writes may also depend on the field they are working in and the specific requirements of the journals they are submitting to.

A hyperprolific author is a scientist or researcher who has an extremely high number of publications in a given time period, typically compared to their peers. This could be in the form of research papers, book chapters, or conference papers.

Hyperprolific authors are often highly productive and dedicated to their research, and may be able to publish many papers in a year due to their ability to work efficiently and effectively. However, it is also possible that some hyperprolific authors may engage in questionable practices, such as network citation, self-plagiarism, salami slicing (splitting a single study into multiple papers), or other forms of misconduct. It is important for scientists to ensure that their work is conducted ethically and in accordance with best practices in order to maintain the integrity of the scientific enterprise [1].

Backscratching, also known as reciprocity, can occur in any professional field, including the scientific community. This refers to the practice of people helping or promoting each other in order to receive some benefit in return. In the scientific community, backscratching could involve scientists promoting each other's work through co-authorship, citing each other's papers, or collaborating on research projects, being editors in journals. While some level of collaboration and mutual support is normal and expected in science, it is important for scientists to ensure that their actions are motivated by the pursuit of scientific knowledge and not by personal gain or the desire to receive favors in return [10].

It is also important to note that the scientific community has established ethical guidelines and practices to ensure that research is conducted with integrity and that the pursuit of knowledge is not compromised by personal or financial interests. These guidelines include the requirement for researchers to disclose any conflicts of interest, such as financial ties or personal relationships, that could influence the interpretation or reporting of their research. Scientists are also expected to follow best practices for research design, data collection, and analysis, and to report their results transparently and accurately. By following these guidelines, scientists can help to maintain the integrity and credibility of the scientific enterprise.

This paper also reveals that the so-called standardized database of the top 2% world scientists is flawed. It includes many science journalists who publish an article twice every week and rank them much higher than any scientist who has to do hard experimental work.

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